

12th International Manikin and Modelling Meeting
29-31 August 2018, St. Gallen, Switzerland

Effect of cotton and synthetic sleepwear on transient sleeping microenvironments

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404554

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Introduction

The amount of sleep needed for optimal health in young adults and adult humans is 7–9 hours per night, which reduces with ageing [1]. Previous research [2,3] into this area shows that hot and humid environments disrupt sleep significantly, commonly resulting in increased wakefulness and reduced amount of NREM and REM sleep. Further, it was also found that the fibre composition of sleepwear could play a vital role in supporting more suitable sleeping microenvironments in hot ambient conditions [4]. Therefore, the present study sought to investigate the effect of selected 100% cotton, cotton rich and synthetic sleepwear and bedding systems on the next to skin microclimate using the sweating thermal manikin, Newton, following a dynamic protocol under controlled steady hot environmental conditions. The objective method was adapted in the present study to determine the possible impact of the selected sleepwear and bedding systems on sleeping microenvironments, and potentially on thermal comfort during sleep and its quality [5].

Materials

The bedding systems for the experimental protocol comprised an inner spring mattress with bed base, wool pillow, a fitted sheet, flat sheet, and pillow cover. A range of 100% cotton, cotton rich and synthetic bedding materials and sleepwear were selected to represent products commonly used in sleep. Bedding and sleepwear combinations were set based on their fibre composition to ensure that entire sleeping systems were consistent for compositions.

Methods

The developed dynamic sleeping experimental protocol was based on the data gained from the background review and comprised several cycles of each NREM (stages 1-4) and REM sleep stages. Skin temperatures ranged between 34.5°C and 36.5°C and varied between sleep stages. Total water loss for the entire sleeping experimental protocol was calculated based on studies of transepidermal losses and also varied between sleep stages. The manikin was operated in heat flux mode with settings varied for each stage of the experimental protocol. Skin temperatures and sweating rates were individually set for each manikin zone and for each sleep stage. The temperature and humidity in the next to skin sleepwear microenvironments were measured using a proprietary developed sensor array and supporting software.

Results and discussion

The results of the study demonstrated that synthetic sleepwear ensembles were hotter and exhibited a higher level of relative humidity in next to skin microenvironments compared to the 100% cotton and cotton rich combinations. Next to skin microenvironment temperatures were up to 1.6°C hotter for the synthetic sleepwear and were consistently more than 1°C higher across all sleep stages. This was also the case for the next to skin microenvironment for relative humidity which was around 8-12% higher for the synthetic sleepwear when compared with the 100% cotton sleepwear. Furthermore, the 100% cotton showed more moderate fluctuations in temperatures and humidity than synthetic sleepwear across the sleep stages. For example, cotton sleepwear demonstrated a smaller change in temperature during REM. It is known that human thermoregulation function is greatly reduced during REM sleep, placing greater importance on the sleep system to maintain sleep quality.

Conclusions

The results of the present study suggested that the fibre composition of sleepwear is a key factor that affects the transient sleeping environment and could play a beneficial role in supporting comfortable bedding microclimates in hot ambient conditions. Further, some sleepwear systems provided lower

microclimate temperature and humidity, along with more moderate changes during sleep stages, suggesting that fibre composition can assist in providing more stable sleep microclimates that can support better sleep.

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